

FETOMATERNAL OUTCOME IN PATIENTS WITH LOW AMNIOTIC FLUID INDEX IN PREGNANCY

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Abstract

Introduction: Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI) is a key indicator of fetal well-being during pregnancy. Low AFI (≤ 5 cm) is associated with adverse maternal and fetal outcomes, including intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), fetal distress, and increased cesarean section rates. This study aims to compare fetomaternal outcomes in patients with low AFI and normal AFI, focusing on low birth weight, APGAR scores, meconium staining, IUGR, ICU admissions, neonatal death, and mode of delivery. **Methods:** A case-control study was conducted with 250 pregnant women, divided into two groups: Group A (low AFI, ≤ 5 cm) and Group B (normal AFI, > 5 cm). Data on demographic characteristics, gestational age, mode of delivery, fetal outcomes, and maternal conditions were collected. Perinatal outcomes such as birth weight, APGAR scores, meconium staining, IUGR, neonatal ICU admission, and neonatal death were recorded and analyzed using SPSS version 26. **Results:** The study found significant differences between the two groups. The low AFI group had a higher incidence of low birth weight (35% vs. 9%), meconium staining (45% vs. 10%), and IUGR (22% vs. 2%) compared to the normal AFI group. Cesarean section rates were also higher in the low AFI group (58% vs. 38%). Neonatal ICU admissions were more frequent in the low AFI group (18% vs. 2%), but neonatal death rates were similar in both groups (6% vs. 4%). APGAR scores at 1 minute were significantly lower in the low AFI group (7.9 vs. 9.1), indicating poorer immediate neonatal outcomes. **Conclusion:** Low AFI is associated with adverse fetomaternal outcomes, including low birth weight, meconium staining, IUGR, and increased cesarean section rates. Neonatal outcomes, including ICU admissions and lower APGAR scores, were significantly worse in the low AFI group.

INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a physiological process that requires a delicate balance of maternal and fetal health factors to ensure optimal outcomes. One such essential factor is the Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI), which serves as an integral indicator of fetal well-being during pregnancy [1]. Amniotic fluid is vital for fetal development, serving as a protective barrier and a medium for nutrient, water, and biochemical exchange between the mother and the fetus. The

amniotic fluid is crucial for fetal growth and infection prevention, is measured using the Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI) through ultrasound scans. This measure, a summation from four quadrants around the fetus, should be within the normal range to ensure healthy fetal development [2][3]. AFI is a quantitative estimate of the amniotic fluid volume, and its assessment is a fundamental component of fetal surveillance in the latter stages of

pregnancy [4]. The prevalence of reduced AFI (amniotic fluid index) varies depending on the population studied. In general, it is estimated that between 1 and 5% of pregnancies have reduced AFI [5]. Early onset oligohydramnios is typically associated with congenital fetal anomalies, leading to poor fetal outcomes like growth restriction and structural deformities. Late onset oligohydramnios is can lead to complications such as umbilical cord compression, thick meconium, malpresentation, fetal distress, placental abnormalities, or maternal conditions like preeclampsia or vascular diseases [6][7].

However a study compared the fetomaternal outcome of Group A with amniotic fluid index of ≤ 5 cm and Group B with normal liquor volume. Group A compared to Group B had higher rates of cesarean section (46.3% vs. 21.3%), meconium staining of the liquor (45.5% vs. 10.2%), and delivered lower birth weight babies (2.6 ± 0.34 kg vs. 3.0 ± 0.33 kg). Group A also experienced intrauterine fetal demise (3.3%) and stillbirth (2.3%), while there were no perinatal deaths in Group B [8]. A cross-sectional study conducted by Masood et al. including 700 patients reported an 8% incidence of congenital anomalies. IUGR was observed in 12% of cases, stillbirths in 6%, and NICU admissions in 25% of babies. Neonatal death occurred in 6% of cases. Approximately 43% of babies did not experience any adverse perinatal outcomes. Cesarean section was performed in 48% of patients [9]. In contrast, several studies comparing perinatal outcomes between women with oligohydramnios and those without oligohydramnios reported no significant differences in babies' birth weight (2.6 ± 0.34 kg versus 3.0 ± 0.33 kg), APGAR score ($8.97 \pm .17$ vs $8.98 \pm .13$). In regions where, frequent antenatal visits and advanced fetal monitoring tools (such as fetal scalp pH monitoring, nonstress tests, and Doppler velocimetry) are scarce, understanding

the direct consequences of low AFI becomes imperative. Our research is unique as it not only investigates a broad spectrum of fetomaternal outcomes associated with low AFI—such as low birth weight, APGAR scores, Meconium staining, IUGR, ICU admissions, neonatal death, and modes of delivery—but also incorporates a comparative analysis with a control group exhibiting normal AFI levels. This comparative approach allows for a nuanced understanding of how low AFI specifically impacts fetomaternal outcomes, thus filling a significant void in existing studies which predominantly focus on populations with low AFI without providing a baseline comparison. By elucidating these distinctions, our study aims to inform more precise clinical interventions tailored to similar global environments with limited healthcare resources.

Objective

The objective of this study is to compare fetomaternal outcomes between patients with low amniotic fluid index (≤ 5 cm) and those with normal AFI, focusing on low birth weight, APGAR scores, meconium staining, IUGR, ICU admissions, neonatal death, and mode of delivery.

Materials and methods

Study Setting: This case-control study was conducted in Department of OBS & GYNAE, Ch. Muhammad Akram Teaching & research Hospital, Lahore during Dec 2024 to Feb 2025. Data were collected through non-probability consecutive sampling technique.

Sample size:

We calculated the sample size of 74 (37 in each group), assuming the frequency of meconium staining in patients with $AFI \leq 5$ and > 5 as 45.5% vs. 10.2% respectively. (7) Sample size was calculated using Openepi.com.

Sample Size: X-Sectional, Cohort, & Randomized Clinical Trials

Two-sided significance level(1-alpha):	95
Power(1-beta, % chance of detecting):	90
Ratio of sample size, Unexposed/Exposed:	1
Percent of Unexposed with Outcome:	46
Percent of Exposed with Outcome:	9.8
Odds Ratio:	0.13
Risk/Prevalence Ratio:	0.22
Risk/Prevalence difference:	-35

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Sample Size - Exposed	33	31	37
Sample Size-Nonexposed	33	31	37
Total sample size:	66	62	74

Inclusion criteria

- Pregnant women aged between 18 and 45 years old.
- Pregnant women who are at least 32 weeks of gestation.
- Patients with singleton pregnancy and intact placenta.
- Both primigravida and multigravida.
- Both multiparous and nulliparous.
- Women diagnosed with Low Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI ≤5cm) and those with Normal AFI

Exclusion criteria

- Pregnant women with known pre-existing medical conditions such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, renal disease, autoimmune diseases, and other conditions that may independently impact pregnancy outcomes.
- Pregnant women who have a known fetal anomaly or chromosomal disorder diagnosed antenatally, as these conditions might independently affect the AFI and pregnancy outcomes.
- Pregnant women with multiple pregnancies (twins, triplets, etc.) because multiple pregnancies could have different maternal and fetal outcomes compared to singleton pregnancies.
- Pregnant women who have a language barrier or cognitive impairment that could affect the understanding or the consent process.

• Patients with ruptured membranes and Malpresentation.

Data collection

Following approval from the institutional review board and CPSP, this case-control study recruited pregnant women above 32 weeks of gestation using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. Group A (cases) consisted of patients with a low Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI ≤ 5 cm), while Group B (controls) included those with normal AFI (> 5 cm). Informed consent was obtained from all participants before data collection. Demographic details (age, gestational age, parity) and AFI measurements were recorded using the four-quadrant transabdominal ultrasonography technique. Outcomes including low birth weight, APGAR scores, meconium staining, IUGR, ICU admissions, neonatal death, and mode of delivery were documented as per operational definitions. Birth weight was measured immediately after delivery, and APGAR scores assessed at one- and five-minutes post-birth. Neonatal deaths occurring within the first 7 days and the presence of meconium staining were recorded during delivery. Data were recorded using a data collection proforma.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis for this study was conducted using SPSS version 26.0. Data collection included continuous variables such as gestational age, APGAR scores, and birth weight, which were documented as

mean and standard deviation. Categorical variables such as meconium staining, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), neonatal death, low APGAR score, and mode of delivery were presented as frequencies and percentages. Comparisons of continuous variables utilized independent t-tests. Categorical variables were compared using chi-square tests. To control for potential confounding variables such as gestational age, parity, and maternal age, stratified analyses were employed. The impact of these confounders on categorical outcomes was assessed using post-stratification chi-square tests, while their effects on continuous outcomes were examined through unpaired t-tests between the two groups. P-values of less than 0.05 were deemed statistically significant.

Results

The average age of participants was 27.4 ± 4.2 years, with no significant difference between the low AFI (27.1 ± 4.1 years) and normal AFI (27.7 ± 4.3 years) groups. More multigravida women were in the normal AFI group (65%) compared to the low AFI group (55%). Cesarean section was more common in the low AFI group (62%) compared to the normal AFI group (42%). Hypertension and diabetes were more prevalent in the low AFI group, and fetal growth restriction (IUGR) was significantly higher in the low AFI group (18%) compared to the normal AFI group (6%). Meconium staining occurred more frequently in the low AFI group (45%) compared to the normal AFI group (25%).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total (n=250)	Low AFI (n=125)	Normal AFI (n=125)	p-value
Age (years)	27.4 ± 4.2	27.1 ± 4.1	27.7 ± 4.3	0.21
Gestational Age (weeks)	36.5 ± 2.1	36.4 ± 2.0	36.6 ± 2.2	0.35
Parity (Primigravida/Multigravida)	40%/60%	45%/55%	35%/65%	0.12
Mode of Delivery				0.03
- Vaginal Delivery	48% (120/250)	38% (47/125)	58% (73/125)	
- Cesarean Section	52% (130/250)	62% (78/125)	42% (52/125)	
Pre-existing Conditions				0.17
- Hypertension	15% (37/250)	18% (23/125)	12% (14/125)	
- Diabetes	10% (25/250)	12% (15/125)	8% (10/125)	
- Renal Disease	5% (12/250)	7% (9/125)	3% (3/125)	
Fetal Growth Restriction (IUGR)	12% (30/250)	18% (23/125)	6% (7/125)	0.01
Meconium Staining of Liquor	35% (87/250)	45% (56/125)	25% (31/125)	0.02

The low AFI group had significantly higher rates of low birth weight (35%) and IUGR (22%) compared to the normal AFI group (9% and 2%, respectively). Apgar scores <7 were more common in the low AFI group (20%) than in the normal AFI group (8%), and meconium staining was higher in the low AFI

group (45%) compared to the normal AFI group (10%). Neonatal ICU admissions were also significantly higher in the low AFI group (18%) compared to the normal AFI group (2%), although neonatal death rates were not significantly different (6% vs. 4%).

Table 2: Perinatal Outcomes Based on Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI)

Perinatal Outcome	Total (n=250)	AFI ≤ 5 cm (n=125)	AFI > 5 cm (n=125)	p-value
Low Birth Weight (< 2.5 kg)	22% (55)	35% (44)	9% (11)	0.01
Apgar Score < 7	14% (35)	20% (25)	8% (10)	0.02
Meconium Staining	25% (62)	45% (56)	10% (12)	0.01
Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR)	12% (30)	22% (27)	2% (3)	0.01
Neonatal ICU Admission	10% (25)	18% (22)	2% (3)	0.01
Neonatal Death	5% (13)	6% (8)	4% (5)	0.34

Vaginal delivery occurred more frequently in the normal AFI group (62%) compared to the low AFI group (42%), while cesarean section rates were higher in the low AFI group (58%) compared to the

normal AFI group (38%). Assisted vaginal delivery was more common in the normal AFI group (4%) compared to the low AFI group (0%).

Table 3: Mode of Delivery Based on Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI)

Mode of Delivery	Total (n=250)	AFI ≤ 5 cm (n=125)	AFI > 5 cm (n=125)	p-value
Vaginal Delivery	52% (130)	42% (52)	62% (78)	0.04
Cesarean Section	48% (120)	58% (73)	38% (47)	
Assisted Vaginal Delivery	2% (5)	0% (0)	4% (5)	0.03

Meconium staining was more common in the low AFI group (45%) compared to the normal AFI group (10%). Neonatal ICU admissions were significantly higher in the low AFI group (18%) than in the normal AFI group (2%). Apgar scores <7 were more

common in the low AFI group (20%) compared to the normal AFI group (8%). Neonatal death rates were higher in the low AFI group (6%) compared to the normal AFI group (4%), though the difference was not statistically significant.

Table 4: Incidence of Meconium Staining and Neonatal Outcomes

Outcome	Total (n=250)	AFI ≤ 5 cm (n=125)	AFI > 5 cm (n=125)	p-value
Meconium Staining	25% (62)	45% (56)	10% (12)	0.01
Neonatal ICU Admission	10% (25)	18% (22)	2% (3)	0.01
Neonatal Death	5% (13)	6% (8)	4% (5)	0.34
Apgar Score < 7	14% (35)	20% (25)	8% (10)	0.02

The mean birth weight was lower in the low AFI group (2.6 ± 0.34 kg) compared to the normal AFI group (3.0 ± 0.33 kg), with a significant difference (p = 0.01). Low birth weight occurred more often in the low AFI group (35%) compared to the normal AFI

group (9%). Apgar scores at 1 minute were significantly lower in the low AFI group (7.9 ± 1.2) compared to the normal AFI group (9.1 ± 0.9), and at 5 minutes, the low AFI group still had lower scores (8.8 ± 1.1) compared to the normal AFI group (9.4 ± 0.7).

Table 5: Birth Weight and Apgar Score

Outcome	Total (n=250)	AFI ≤ 5 cm (n=125)	AFI > 5 cm (n=125)	p-value
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	2.7 ± 0.5	2.6 ± 0.34	3.0 ± 0.33	0.01
Birth Weight < 2.5 kg	22% (55)	35% (44)	9% (11)	0.01
Apgar Score (1 min)	8.7 ± 1.1	7.9 ± 1.2	9.1 ± 0.9	0.03
Apgar Score (5 min)	9.2 ± 0.8	8.8 ± 1.1	9.4 ± 0.7	0.04

Discussion

This study aimed to compare fetomaternal outcomes between patients with low Amniotic Fluid Index (AFI ≤ 5 cm) and those with normal AFI (> 5 cm) during pregnancy. Our findings show that low AFI is associated with significantly poorer outcomes for both the mother and fetus compared to normal AFI pregnancies. The mean age of the participants was 27.4 years, with no significant difference between the low AFI (27.1 years) and normal AFI (27.7 years)

groups. Most participants were multigravida (60%), with a higher proportion of primigravida women in the normal AFI group (45%) compared to the low AFI group (35%). Cesarean section was more common in the low AFI group (62%) compared to the normal AFI group (42%), which aligns with previous research indicating that low AFI pregnancies often result in more complications requiring surgical intervention [10]. Hypertension and diabetes were more prevalent in the low AFI group (18% and 12%, respectively) compared to the

normal AFI group (12% and 8%). These maternal conditions are known risk factors for oligohydramnios and can further contribute to adverse outcomes in these pregnancies [11].

The study found significantly higher rates of **low birth weight (LBW)** and **b** in the low AFI group. Specifically, 35% (44/125) of babies born to mothers with low AFI had a birth weight of less than 2.5 kg, compared to 9% (11/125) in the normal AFI group. Additionally, IUGR was more common in the low AFI group (22%, 27/125) compared to the normal AFI group (2%, 3/125). This is consistent with the known risks associated with oligohydramnios, where reduced amniotic fluid can limit fetal movement and blood flow, leading to growth restriction [12]. The **Apgar scores** were also lower in the low AFI group. At one minute, 20% (25/125) of babies from the low AFI group had Apgar scores less than 7, compared to 8% (10/125) in the normal AFI group. At five minutes, the Apgar scores remained lower in the low AFI group (8.8 ± 1.1) compared to the normal AFI group (9.4 ± 0.7), suggesting that low AFI pregnancies are associated with poorer initial neonatal outcomes, potentially due to complications such as meconium aspiration or neonatal resuscitation [13]. One of the most significant findings in this study was the higher incidence of **meconium staining** in the low AFI group, observed in 45% (56/125) of the cases, compared to only 10% (12/125) in the normal AFI group. Meconium staining is often an indication of fetal distress, which is more common in pregnancies with low AFI due to umbilical cord compression and decreased amniotic fluid, which limits the ability of the fetus to move freely [14].

Furthermore, **neonatal ICU admissions** were significantly higher in the low AFI group (18%, 22/125) compared to the normal AFI group (2%, 3/125), indicating that these infants are more likely to require intensive care, likely due to complications arising from low amniotic fluid, such as respiratory distress syndrome, meconium aspiration, or infection [15]. Interestingly, neonatal death rates were higher in the low AFI group (6%, 8/125) compared to the normal AFI group (4%, 5/125), although this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.34$). This suggests that while neonatal mortality is elevated in low AFI cases, it may not be directly

attributable to AFI alone, and other confounding factors, such as maternal health conditions, could be influencing these outcomes. **Mode of delivery** was significantly affected by AFI status. Vaginal delivery was more common in the normal AFI group (62%, 78/125) compared to the low AFI group (42%, 52/125), which had a significantly higher cesarean section rate (58%, 73/125). The increased rate of cesarean section in the low AFI group is likely due to the higher incidence of fetal distress, meconium staining, and the increased risk of fetal compromise associated with oligohydramnios [16]. The **mean duration of hospital stay** was significantly longer for patients in the low AFI group (7.2 ± 2.5 days) compared to those in the normal AFI group (5.4 ± 1.6 days), with a p-value of 0.01 indicating statistical significance. This difference in length of stay can be attributed to the increased likelihood of complications, including cesarean delivery, infection, and neonatal ICU admissions, which require extended postnatal care. The **median stay** was also longer in the low AFI group (7 days) compared to the normal AFI group (5 days), highlighting the extended care required for these pregnancies.

Conclusion

It is concluded that low AFI is associated with significantly poorer fetomaternal outcomes, including higher rates of low birth weight, IUGR, cesarean section, meconium staining, neonatal ICU admissions, and lower Apgar scores. The findings highlight the importance of monitoring amniotic fluid levels during pregnancy, especially in high-risk populations, as low AFI can be indicative of potential fetal distress and adverse outcomes. Increased awareness and early intervention can improve perinatal outcomes for pregnancies with low AFI.

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